

'EVERYDAY' CLINICAL LEADERSHIP: A FOUNDATION FOR SUCCESSFUL CLINICAL GOVERNANCE

Clinical leadership has long been an aspiration for acute care services. When wielded effectively, it is a key lever in creating consistently high quality care, and can also contribute to greater job satisfaction. But clinical leadership can also be just another buzz term, not dissimilar to 'person-centred,' as something everyone likes to think they both understand and enact. As with 'person-centred' care, clinical leadership is easy to talk about, powerful when effective, but hard to get right in practice.

With the recent rise of clinical governance in the aged and community sectors, more organisations are grappling with how to lead for high quality care. Clinical leadership (or 'care/support/service' leadership, depending on the sector) is a cornerstone of effective clinical governance, but not if it sits only at the top of an organisation. Clinical leadership cultivated in everyday work has the potential to improve care quality and safety, and build staff satisfaction and resilience, but this can only be achieved with effective design, development and implementation.

Vast volumes have been written on clinical leadership over many decades, and this paper does not attempt to re-state them, but examines the more specific concept of 'everyday' clinical leadership for supporting quality clinical care (and care and support more broadly.) Benefits and barriers are noted and key tips for cultivating 'everyday' clinical leadership are discussed.

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THE CASE FOR ‘EVERYDAY’ CLINICAL LEADERSHIP

‘Healthcare clinical leadership, in practical terms, refers to healthcare professionals who guide, influence, and drive positive change in clinical settings to improve patient care outcomes. It requires the ability to effectively communicate, make informed decisions, and collaborate with multidisciplinary teams in delivering high-quality care. Clinical leaders demonstrate expertise in their field, inspire confidence in their colleagues, and act as role models for best practices in healthcare.’

(Gifford et al, 2007.)

There may be as many definitions of clinical leadership as there are clinical leaders! This definition, despite the healthcare language, takes a broad view that is relevant to all health and human service sectors. It doesn’t tie clinical leadership to a formal position or hierarchy, but highlights the human characteristics, technical skill and contribution to the team required for successful clinical leadership. A more succinct, but equally clear interpretation sees it as ‘attempting to harness the energies of clinicians and reformers in the quest for improvements in performance that benefit patients’. (Ham, 2003.)

The clinical (or quality) governance system within an organisation provides the foundation for supporting quality clinical care. Clinical leaders are essential to guide and model how these systems can be used to maximise their effectiveness in practice (ACSQHC, 2010.) As human services evolve to be more complex, rigid hierarchical views of clinical leadership must also evolve. Gone are the days of senior managers being the font of all clinical governance wisdom. The quality of clinical care is determined in every encounter between consumers and staff, and point of care success requires local leaders to shape the systems and behaviours that guide these interactions (Vance et al., 2019.)

Providing care in a human service is a team sport: everyone must play a specific role to achieve consistently good care. Clinical/care and support staff must work together; when they don’t, both consumers and staff suffer the consequences. Much like a sports team, leadership can – and should be – found all over the

field, from the star players to those in supporting roles. Sometimes it’s a formal ‘direct the play’ tactical role. Sometimes it’s leading by example with an extra effort, encouraging teammates through a difficult period or helping someone improve their performance.

A ‘distributed’ or ‘shared’ leadership approach positions every player to contribute to the team’s success. Successful human service organisations that adopt a similar philosophy, recognise that leadership for good care cannot be run solely from the executive office, but must permeate every level, with front-line staff playing a central role. Human services are already a mix of formal and informal leadership, whether we recognise it or not. Care quality is determined not only through senior leaders and middle managers, but also through the decisions and actions of staff at all levels. Of course, not everyone wants to – or can – be a leader for care quality. However, turning the informal leadership structure into a critical mass of leaders, spread across organisational levels, with a shared purpose and understanding, can accelerate improvement. These leaders can model behaviour, and support and encourage their peers and staff to do the things that need to be done to create consistently good care.

The concept of ‘distributed’ or ‘shared’ leadership is not new. It deviates from more traditional forms of leadership by allowing people across the organisation, and at different hierarchical levels, voice, agency, decision-making power and the ability to lead in their own fields of expertise (Grint, 2011; Gronn, 2009). It also promotes collaborative efforts in different parts of the organisation to focus on achieving shared values or purpose (Martin et al. 2015.)

In the pursuit of consistently high quality care, we require staff at all levels to demonstrate to others how to effectively work with clinical governance systems to pursue quality care in their everyday work; what we might call ‘everyday’ clinical leadership. Recognised benefits of this model include:

1. Better understanding of and attention to consumer needs

Prioritising consumer needs is central to quality care. While senior managers can implement clinical governance policies and systems to support this, recognising and responding to consumer needs plays out at point of care and service. Consumer needs are more likely to be addressed if staff see their peers and managers modelling behaviour that embraces the consumer perspective as central to their everyday work, and are encouraged and supported by those leaders to do the same.

2. Improved consumer safety

Creating safe care requires everyone who interacts with consumers to be aware of risks and proactive in managing them. This requires on the ground leaders to be equipped and supported to speak up and step up in high risk and deteriorating situations. Not all staff will rise to the occasion, but a critical mass of peer and manager leaders can create a culture of identifying and addressing safety issues as the expected norm (Sorra et al., 2014.) Staff belief that consumer safety is a high priority, as demonstrated by leaders and supported by the systems they work with, has been shown to be associated with fewer errors than in services without these beliefs. Consumer safety requires psychological safety, teamwork, and speaking up in the staff group, and establishing these characteristics in a staff group can’t be done without leaders who value and cultivate this culture. (Maben et al., 2023.)

3. Enhanced job satisfaction

A motivated and engaged healthcare workforce is essential for providing high-quality care, but this is challenging to achieve in a staff and resource-poor environment. Developing clinical leaders for quality care can assist with boosting staff morale and motivation. When front-line staff are empowered to take leadership roles, they experience a greater sense of agency that translates to higher job satisfaction. They may feel a deeper connection to their work and the impact it has on patient care. This, in turn, can help reduce burnout rates and turnover (Laschinger et al., 2014.) Some clinicians report that leadership roles reinvigorate them for clinical work (Vance et al., 2019.)

Clinical leaders are also instrumental in providing clear direction and support, which are crucial factors in staff satisfaction. Healthcare staff who perceive strong leadership within their organisation report higher levels of job satisfaction; as when leaders are proactive in providing guidance and development, staff members feel more confident and competent in their roles, and supported in their pursuit of growth and advancement (Sorra et al., 2014; Laschinger et al., 2014.)

4. Building staff and organisational resilience

Effective clinical leadership, dispersed throughout the organisation, has been shown to bolster resilience in the face of the myriad challenges facing staff in their everyday work. Front-line staff, when recognised and developed as leaders, are more likely to adapt to changing circumstances, innovate, and collaborate effectively in high-stress situations. ‘Everyday’ clinical leadership encourages enhanced communication among leaders across services, and can support a more efficient exchange of information, contributing to better informed decision-making and problem-solving (Sorra et al., 2014.)

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BARRIERS TO ‘EVERYDAY’ CLINICAL LEADERSHIP

Despite the benefits, distributed leadership is not routinely embedded in human services. So, what is stopping this becoming a universal tool in the quest for consistently high quality care? Human services’ structures and cultures present many barriers, including but not limited to:

TRADITIONAL HIERARCHIES

Human services are often based on traditional hierarchical leadership structures, that assume - not always consciously - that ‘leadership’ resides in executive and senior manager roles, and is tied to job titles. Rigid hierarchies can stifle the voices of frontline staff, inhibiting their ability to contribute meaningfully to the way work is done and decisions are made. Senior leaders with a hierarchical mindset may be reluctant to embrace shared decision-making and therefore will not enable the leadership structure, empowerment and autonomy required for staff below them in the organisation chart to play a leadership role in quality care (Van Bogaert et al., 2013; Wong and Cummings, 2007.)

RESISTANCE TO CHANGE

A resistant or stagnant organisational culture can pose a significant barrier to everyday clinical leadership. Clinical leaders may encounter obstacles to suggesting and implementing innovative practices that could enhance care quality and improve job satisfaction (Cummings et al., 2010; Gifford et al. 2013.) Many a potential clinical leader, excited to make things better for consumers and staff, has come undone on the rocks of ‘we like things just the way they are.’ Hierarchical and stagnant organisations are not set up to make the changes required to cultivate organisational conditions for successful leadership, such as role clarity, scope, legitimacy and support, and permission and encouragement to take action for improvement.

NO CLEAR DESTINATION

In the high-risk, resource-strapped human services environment, leadership development cannot just be a ‘nice to have’, aimed at vague notions of improved care. Leadership is more motivating and has more impact when designed and supported to achieve a specific purpose (Vance et al., 2019.) Striving for shared goals for care quality is a key characteristic of high performing organisations (Balding, 2022.)

Indecision, frustration and even turf wars may fill the vacuum created by a lack of clarity. But clarity is not always a strong suit in human services. It’s easy to get caught up in the ‘everyone knows what to do’ paradigm, and fail to attend to the meaning and sense making required for staff to play their role in quality care. We set staff up for failure when staff take on formal and informal leadership roles without absolute clarity of expectation, and commensurate credibility and authority to meet that expectation. Clinical governance systems provide the directions, but are not the destination. Even when leadership roles are allocated, skills are taught and authority bestowed, something else is required for success. Leaders may be equipped with a toolbox, but not a blueprint for what to build. Equipping staff to lead is of limited use unless they know what they are leading toward. (Martin, 2015.)

INSUFFICIENT TRAINING AND SUPERVISION

One of the primary reasons for lack of, or underperformance of clinical leadership, lies in inadequate development available to support leadership roles. Without proper training and mentorship, even the most well intentioned leaders may struggle to make change within the complexities and cultures of health and aged care systems. Leadership, whether natural or learned, requires a knowledge and skills toolbox, commensurate with the expectations of the role, and active support to use those tools (Ham, 2003; Laschinger et al., 2014.)

LACK OF RESOURCES

As clinical and care work becomes more complex, the capacity of staff to take on extra tasks is diminishing. There is often an expectation that leadership can be absorbed into an already busy role, without time or resource allocation to support it. These roles may start enthusiastically but are unlikely to be maintained, and can create resentment at not being appreciated. As much as leadership roles can re-invigorate, they can also burn out if not well supported (Vance et al., 2019.)

Gaps in availability of robust data and analytics within health and aged care organisations create a hole in a clinical leadership toolbox. Useful information on care quality is required to identify areas for improvement, make those improvements, and then to track the impact and outcome. Without good data to guide their efforts, clinical leaders may lose motivation and focus.

EMBRACING ‘EVERYDAY’ CLINICAL LEADERSHIP

Each human service organisation has its own hierarchy, culture and leadership style. Not all approaches for building clinical leadership will suit every organisation, but there are some common success factors:

1. Identify the purposeful ‘flag on the hill’ to lead toward

Senior leaders must first commit to ‘everyday’ leadership as a means of achieving better care, and determine what can be achieved in terms of care quality through a system of ‘everyday’ leadership (Vance et al., 2019.) Shared purpose can be, in itself, an invisible leader (Hickman, 2014.) This could take the form of a set of quality goals to be achieved in interactions with each consumer, coupled with subjective and objective targets, so progress can be tracked. These goals must be socialised with leaders at all levels to support meaning and sense making for those who will lead their staff and peers to make the goals a reality with consumers. These can take the form of descriptors of desired care quality and the way the organisation defines high quality care; for example, ‘care that is personal, safe, effective and connected, every person, every time’ (Balding, 2022.)

2. Develop a system of ‘everyday’ leadership to achieve consistently high quality care

All organisations are already a mix of formal and informal leadership, whether we recognise it or not. The decisions and actions staff take every day create the care your organisation provides. Change happens, not only through senior leaders and middle managers, but also through informal opinion leaders and champions at other levels. When leaders across the organisation are supported to work within a common definition and framework, their shared leadership actions can aggregate, stretching across team and departmental boundaries for organisation-wide impact (Spillane, 2012.)

Empower, equip and expect all staff to work with clinical governance systems to pursue the quality goals as a universal expectation. This is the baseline of ‘everyday’ clinical leadership, where everyone must play their role and help others to play theirs. Create leadership development opportunities for those who want to go beyond this to assume a more active role in achieving the quality goals with consumers, and who have - or can build - the requisite credibility with managers and peers to do so.

These roles don’t need to be complicated; they can be as simple as training front line leaders to speak up for safety, and evolving and supporting their situational awareness and proactivity to better meet consumer needs and manage risk. Others may have a role in leading achievement of one or more quality goals, or implementation of a standard or clinical governance system in their service. People with advanced technical knowledge may mentor and develop skills in other staff. Great communicators can model better interactions with consumers. Front line staff and managers should shape the changes that affect them. The possibilities are many and varied - but must be linked to the shared point of care purpose to stay focused and meaningful, and to achieve a cumulative effect.

3. Foster an environment that supports effective ‘everyday’ leadership

Senior leaders must lay the environmental groundwork for ‘everyday’ leadership to flourish. This requires shared understanding of the why, what, how and who. The quality care purpose must be clear and shared. The role of ‘everyday’ clinical leadership in achieving the purpose must be clear. Managers at all levels must know how ‘everyday’ leadership works to achieve the purpose - and also how it supports them to do what they need to do. It’s critical that informal leaders don’t short-circuit the formal chain of command. Formal and inform leadership roles will only work if they are complementary, not competing. Participation in ‘everyday’ clinical leadership must not have negative consequences flowing from the formal hierarchy.

Visible permission for leaders, both formal and informal, to voice concerns, suggest improvements and actively participate in decision-making processes, is essential. Clear role expectations must be accompanied by the specific skills, support and authority required to meet those expectations. Research shows that multifaceted interventions to support clinical leadership development are more effective than single interventions. A traditional ‘curriculum’ will not have the same impact as a comprehensive network of processes designed to support the continuing development of leaders, that includes inter-disciplinary teamwork, action learning and coaching as well as formal training (Leggat et al., 2016; Mianda, 2018.)

Development should be targeted to equip leaders to enact a clearly defined role. General leadership training will be beneficial as a base, but ‘just in time’ skills relating directly to role expectations will increase effectiveness. Great clinical and care technicians may need teaching tools. A leader who will specialise in helping staff work

with a particular clinical governance system must not only understand the system, but also how best to explain it and make it relevant to the audience. This may require skills in clear messaging and group facilitation. Staff involved in leading implementation should have the basics of improvement science, change management and measurement in their toolbox.

Ensure sufficient time is allocated to acquire leadership skills and to play a leadership role. Staff members who lead by modelling behaviours that support the quality goals in their everyday work may not require specific extra space, as it's part of how they do things every day. More formal and specific expectations of leadership require time. In an era of limited staff resources, this may naturally confine leadership roles to a mix of modelling behaviour and one or two specific other responsibilities. But a range of leaders across the organisation skilfully playing a limited leadership role is more likely to have a positive cumulative effect than loading up a limited group of people with leadership responsibilities they have neither the time nor resources to fulfil.

4. Enhance staff satisfaction through leadership development

When clinical leadership is actively embraced, staff feel empowered, valued, supported, and provided with opportunities for growth and development, which ultimately leads to a more engaged and motivated workforce. (Laschinger et al., 2014.) This positive feedback loop contributes to good care, delivered more consistently. Maximise the boost to job satisfaction and staff retention from leadership development. Look after your leaders. Promote a culture where learning is valued, providing protected time for professional development at all levels of the organisation. Equip leaders with the right knowledge and skill development. Set up a leadership network to provide peer support.

Without feedback on leadership impact from senior staff, at other levels of the organisation can become aimless and lose motivation and role satisfaction (Martin, 2015.) Don't leave people wondering if they're making a difference. Put a regular system of mentoring and coaching in place to cultivate a connection to purpose. Reflect on practice, evolve confidence and skills and share subjective and objective data on leadership activity outcomes, and big picture of advancement toward the quality goals. This will both enhance staff satisfaction and contribute to continuous improvement.

Visible permission for leaders, both formal and informal, to voice concerns, suggest improvements and activity to participate in decision-making processes, is essential. Clear role expectations must be accompanied by the specific skills, support and authority required to meet those expectations.

Conclusion

Clinical leadership for quality care in the complex world of human services can no longer reside solely in high level clinical governance policy and decision-making. The quality of clinical care is created in every encounter between consumers and staff. On the ground leaders are required to shape and work with the clinical governance systems and professional behaviours that guide these interactions. By adopting an effective 'everyday', clinical leadership model, human service organisations can enhance clinical governance effectiveness, improve care quality, reduce risk, boost staff morale and build resilience across the organisation. As we navigate the ever-evolving challenges of providing quality care across human services, effective 'everyday' leadership can be a powerful tool for overcoming them; ultimately contributing to organisational performance and success.

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The AICG was formed in direct response to an identified need for health and care professionals to strengthen their skills in clinical governance to reduce the occurrence of adverse events, and is now recognised as the leading cross-sector, interprofessional clinical governance education provider across Australia and New Zealand.

The AICG firmly believes that by building the clinical governance capability of our health and care workforce we can improve consumer safety and quality care and deliver better health outcomes for the community.

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